

STUDY OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RETAIL SECTOR IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Indian retail sector is one of the most sought after sectors that carry great potential for attracting FDI. Foreign Direct Investment refers to capital inflows from abroad that is invested in or to enhance the production capacity of the economy. Foreign Investment in India is governed by the FDI policy announced by the Government of India and the provision of the Foreign Exchange Management Act (FEMA) 1999. The foreign investors are free to invest in India, except few sectors/activities, where prior approval from the RBI or Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) would be required. Many foreign retailers have also entered the market through different routes such as wholesale cash-and-carry, local manufacturing, franchising, test marketing etc. With the growth in organized retailing, unorganized retailers are fast changing their business models and implementing new technologies and modern accounting practices to face competition. The growing market has attracted foreign investors and India has been portrayed as an important investment destination for the global retail chains.

KEYWORDS

FDI, Retail Sector, FEMA, FIPB etc.

INTRODUCTION

Retailing is defined as all activities involved in selling goods or services directly to final consumers for their personal, non-business use via shops, markets, door-to-door selling, and mail order or over the internet, where the buyer intends to consume the product through personal, family or household dues. Retailing involves a direct interface with the customer and the coordination of business activities from end to end- right from the concept or design stage of a product or offering, to its delivery and post delivery service to the customer. The industry has contributed to the economic growth of many countries and is undoubtedly one of the fastest changing and dynamic industries in the world today. FDI has been recognized as an important driver for economic growth and development. One of the most striking developments during the last two decades is the spectacular growth of FDI in the global economic landscape. This unprecedented growth of global FDI in 1990 around the world make FDI an important and vital component of development strategy in both developed and developing nations and policies are designed in order to stimulate inward flows. In fact, FDI provides a win – win situation to the host and the home countries. Both countries are directly interested in inviting FDI, because they benefit a lot from such type of investment.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- To study present regulatory framework for FDI in general and in retail sector.
- To study the inflow of FDI in different sectors in India.
- To study various entry options available to global retailers in India.

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

Foreign Direct Investment refers to capital inflows from abroad that is invested in or to enhance the production capacity of the economy. FDI is investment in a foreign country through the acquisition of a local company or the establishment there of an operation on a new site. Foreign direct investment is investment of foreign assets into domestic structures, equipment, and organizations.

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR FDI IN INDIA

Foreign Investment in India is governed by the FDI policy announced by the Government of India and the provision of the Foreign Exchange Management Act (FEMA) 1999. The Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India is the nodal agency for motoring and reviewing the FDI policy on continued basis and changes in sectoral policy/ sectoral equity cap. The FDI policy is notified through Press Notes by the Secretariat for Industrial Assistance (SIA), Department of Industrial Policy and

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Promotion (DIPP). The foreign investors are free to invest in India, except few sectors/activities, where prior approval from the RBI or Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) would be required. *Indian companies can receive FDI under two routes:*

Automatic Route: It does not require prior approval either of Reserve Bank of India (RBI) or government. It is allowed in all activities / sectors except where the provisions of consolidated FDI policy paragraph as- entry route for investment issued by government of India from time to time are attracted.

Government Route: Government route means that investment in the capital of resident entities by non-resident entities can be made only with the prior approval from FIPB, Ministry of Finance or SIA, DIPP as the case may be. FDI in sectors, not covered under automatic route requires prior approval of the government, which is considered by Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB), Department of Economic Affairs, and Ministry of Finance.

FDI INFLOWS IN DIFFERENT SECTORS IN INDIA

Table-1

Ranks	Sector	2012-13 (April- March)	2013-14 (April- March)	2014-15 (April- March)	Cumulative Inflows (April 2000 -March 2015)	%age to total Inflows (In terms of US \$)
1.	Service Sector	26,306 (4,833)	13,294 (2,225)	19,963 (3,253)	205,532 (42,713)	17%
2	Construction Development: Townships, Housing, Built-up Infrastructure	7,248 (1,332)	7,508 (1,226)	4,582 (758)	113,140 (24,064)	10%
3	Telecommunication	1,654 (304)	7,987 (1,307)	17,372 (2,895)	84,092 (17,058)	7%
4	Computer Software & Hardware	2,656 (486)	6,896 (1,126)	13,564 (2,200)	73,235 (15,017)	6%
5	Drugs & Pharmaceuticals	6,011 (1,123)	7,191 (1,279)	9,211 (1,523)	65,282 (13,121)	5%
6	Automobile Industry	8,384 (1,537)	9,027 (1,517)	15,794 (2,570)	63,991 (12,383)	5%
7	Chemicals (other than Fertilizers)	1,596 (292)	4,738 (878)	4,077 (669)	49,310 (10,337)	4%
8	Power	2,923 (536)	6,519 (1,066)	3,985 (657)	46,640 (9,557)	4%
9	Metallurgical Industries	7,878 (1,466)	3,436 (568)	2,897 (472)	41,147 (8,547)	3%
10	Trading	3,901 (718)	8,191 (1,343)	16,962 (2,761)	43,799 (8060)	3%

Sources: Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion, Government of India, Ministry of Commerce and Industry

ENTRY OPTIONS TO FOREIGN PLAYERS IN RETAIL SECTOR

Manufacturing and Local Sourcing: Companies that set up manufacturing facilities are allowed to sell the products in the domestic market. Consumer durable companies such as Sony and Samsung have entered the retail sector through this route. Due to high labour cost in their domestic market, many international brands are setting up manufacturing bases in developing countries such as India and China and/or are sourcing products from local manufacturers. For example, Levi's and Tommy Hilfiger are sourcing products from Indian manufacturers like Arvind Mills. Other international brands like GIVO from Italy have set up export oriented manufacturing facilities. These companies are allowed to sell products to Indian consumers through franchising, local distributors, existing Indian retailers, own outlets etc. Companies, which have set up manufacturing bases or are sourcing products from India, would continue to do so if FDI is allowed in retailing. With increased globalization, companies are and in future would source their products from countries where they have efficiency and cost advantages.

Franchising: Franchising is the most preferred mode through which foreign players have entered the Indian market. According to foreign respondents, it is the easiest route to enter the Indian market. Franchising is often used as a mode to expand the market of a particular retail enterprise outside domestic economy since it allows firms to expand without investing their own capital, is based on local expertise and enables firms to circumvent local oppositions and regulations. This is the most common mode for entry of fast food chains across the world. Apart from fast food chains like Pizza Hut, players such as Lacoste, Mango, Nike, Mars, and Spencer have entered the Indian market through this route.

Test Marketing: Test marketing is another route through which many foreign players have entered the Indian market. Foreign Investment Promotion Board (FIPB) allows foreign companies to test market products for a two-year period by the end of which they are required to set up manufacturing facilities in India. Direct selling companies like Amway and Oriflamme entered the Indian market through this route. Initially, Amway got an approval for test marketing for a period of two years but they managed to secure an extension of one more year. At the end of the third year, they set up contract manufacturing facilities and brought in foreign investment and technical knowledge. Oriflamme too extended its manufacturing facility in Noida for producing certain specific products. Other products are imported and would continue to be imported from abroad. The test-marketing route allows foreign players to test the demand for their products in Indian market before undertaking investment. Many foreign players would like to enter the Indian market through this route.

Wholesale Cash-and-Carry Operation: The wholesale Cash-and-Carry operation is defined as any trading outlets where goods are sold at the wholesale rate for retailers and businesses to buy. The transactions are only for business purposes and not for personal consumption as in the case of retailing. Large international retailers such as Germany's Metro cash & Carry GmbH and Shoprite Checkers of South Africa have entered the Indian market through this route. Metro GmbH was the first company to bring 100% FDI through this route. The company has been given license to supply to distributors, wholesalers and retailers having valid trade licenses/ sales registration. Metro, which is one of the top five global retailers, had initially set up two outlets in the suburbs of the city of Bangalore. Customers of Metro include retailers, hotels, commercial organizations and organization of professionals like doctors, lawyers, IT, etc.

Distribution: Companies such as Swarovski and Hugo Boss have set up distribution offices in India and these offices supply the products to local Indian retailers. All products of Hugo Boss are imported and distributed through the company's distributor.

Through Special Permission: The Sri Lankan retailers have entered the Indian market through the initiatives of Export Development Board of Sri Lanka (EDB), which obtain special permission from the RBI to set up retail operations in India. This mode has allowed retailers from Sri Lanka to enter the Indian market without domestic manufacturing and sourcing conditions and some products sold by these traders are similar to those sold by Indian retailers, EDB did not face any opposition from Chambers, retailers and the trading houses.

CONCLUSION

By completely opening this sector, the government has strongly conveyed its willingness in retail sector reforms. By allowing FDI in retail trade, India will significantly benefit in terms of quality standards since the inflow of FDI in retail sector is bound to pull up the quality standards and cost-competitiveness of Indian producers and marketers in all the segments. It will also help in integrating the modern Indian retail market with that of the global retail market. More chances of respectful status and better pay packets for retail staff, which the unorganized sector has failed to provide to the masses employed. Along with existing legal and regulatory framework, strong enforcement mechanism is necessary to ensure that big retailers do not dislocate small retailers by unfair means and there is peaceful coexistence of both the arms of retail sector.

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